

EXPERIMENTAL DETERMINATION OF AGEING AND DEGRADATION OF GLASS FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES IN PETROCHEMICAL APPLICATIONS

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Introduction

In the Oil and Gas industry the operating environment for the equipment and especially for steel pipelines can be extremely aggressive, and even corrosion resistant alloys (including highly alloyed stainless steel) can corrode. After being in service for a period of time, a pipe can fail because of the nature of some of the chemicals being transported or stored, which is unacceptable. As a result of this the operational cost for the industry is increased due to increased maintenance. In addition, the installation costs for metal pipes are great because these materials are heavy compared to composite pipes.

One solution successfully adopted is the use of glass reinforced plastics (GRP), and such pipes have been already installed for hundreds of kilometres. GRP has been used in other industries for its high specific strength and stiffness to weight ratio where its low corrosion resistance has been a secondary benefit. For the oil and gas industry the priority is reversed, and one of the most important benefits being these materials are less vulnerable to harsh environments.

Nowadays, GRP is used to transfer or store chlorine, chlorate, and various types of acids such as used in desulphurization plants. It is now employed generally in every structural application in oil and gas production. Because of the environmentally hostile nature of these chemicals, even GRP equipment needs regular maintenance in order to prevent failure. In many instances a thermoplastic liner is also used to act as a corrosion or permeation barrier and this lining may be nylon, polypropylene, polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) or polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE). However, after decades of being in service, the pipe liners can become severely damaged, and eventually the GRP pipe itself is attacked by chemicals, resulting in

degradation which reduces its property levels and, finally, even catastrophic failure (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 Failure in aqueous alkaline at 70°C causing a fatality; courtesy of G. Bergman - see reference [1]

As the oil and gas industry begins looking to new horizons beyond current resources, such as in ultra-deep water, ultra deep wells, arctic conditions or highly sour reservoirs, composite materials may become the only economically viable structural material available. But because even GRPs are not completely resistant to hostile fluids a test methodology is required to enable assessment of likely service life. This laboratory is part-way through a project aimed at providing such information. The present paper gives a status report on work so far. Before discussing the data obtained, some background theory and previous work are outlined.

Definition of Ageing

It is known that the environment can have a great influence on materials and can result in corrosion. In metals, there is literature that explains the creation and propagation of deleterious effects. Analogously,

in GRPs and in polymers in general, the environment can cause both reversible and irreversible changes to the original property magnitudes. The process of polymer property levels changing over time is termed “ageing” and in particular can be categorized by three different primary mechanisms: (i) physical, (ii) chemical and (iii) mechanical. These mechanisms are highly dependent on the material characteristics (for example thickness, density, type of matrix etc.) as well as the application, environment and length of exposure.

(i) Physical ageing will occur in polymers at temperatures above and below the glass transition temperature (T_g). It is based on fluid absorption. Initially, the fluid adsorbs into the GRP surface, and then as time progresses, a fluid content concentration gradient develops through the thickness of the material by diffusion. Diffusion characteristics can be measured by mass uptake measurements.

Physical ageing is the most basic feature of ageing and can be made reversible in amorphous polymers by heating the polymer. Using FRPs, this simple process becomes more complex than for homogeneous polymers. For some GRPs, there may be a different concentration along continuous fibres (or fibre matrix interfaces) rather than across them. Moisture or temperature cycling can lead to local dryness at the surface plies compared to the centre of the laminate. The moisture distribution can lead to significant residual stresses within the laminate that can in turn alter the rate of diffusion and in severe cases cause ply delamination or blisters. Moreover, these effects could result in changes in the free volume (the free space between molecular chains) and also in mass, tensile and flexural strength. [2, 3] Cracks can eventually occur, especially below T_g .

(ii) Chemical ageing, in contrast, is an irreversible procedure, as chemical changes occur. It affects the polymer chains through mechanisms such as cross-link creation and addition of chemical side groups. It starts at the surface and continues inward. It can be characterized by changes in the T_g , mechanical property levels. [1, 3], and cracking.

(iii) Mechanical ageing is also an irreversible process, affecting the bulk material. It is brought about by the application of force, either cycling or continuous. It includes matrix cracking, delamination, interface degradation and all processes

that are observable on the macroscopic scale. It is difficult to understand how the ageing mechanisms are propagated and defined [1], but both physical and chemical ageing can influence its rate or onset.

Ageing in Laboratory

Much work has already been done in ageing mechanisms in laboratories. As a result, nowadays, there are useful literature and tests for providing information about pipe design and maintenance. Examples of relevant standards are:

- ASTM C581: Requires immersion of a material in a fluid at a single temperature. Properties such as Barcol hardness, flexural modulus, strength and glass transition temperature (T_g) are determined taking measurements over the period of one year. If the rate of property magnitude loss is less than a prescribed level, then the material can be approved for long-term usage. [4]
- NACE TM0298-2003: Evaluates the compatibility of FRP pipe and tubulars for various oilfield applications. There is a test plan of exposure for 160 hours for non- acids, and 6 hours for acids. However, there are not any pass or failure criteria and the use of this standard only indicates the performance of the FRP pipe in a laboratory test, and there is not any relation with service performance. [5]
- BS EN 13121-2:2003: Determines requirement factors for chemical resistance of GRP tanks and vessels. In part 1, using a number of tables with materials, temperatures and media, the chemical and thermal resistance to the service conditions can be established. Part 2, establishes whether the pipe has the required chemical and thermal resistance for the service conditions. [6]
- ISO 24817 Petroleum, Petrochemical and Natural Gas Industries – Composite Repairs for Pipe work – Qualification and Design, Installation, Testing and Inspection: The scope of this standard is to give requirements for the design, installation, testing and inspection for the application of composite repairs to damaged steel pipes. [7]
- ISO 14692 Petroleum and Natural Gas Industries – Glass-reinforced plastics (GRP) piping: This describes how to qualify and manufacture GRP pipes and indicates how to fabricate, install and operate pipes and fittings in industry. The test plan

requires an exposure of a material in a fluid for 1000h up to 3 times the design pressure and at least 7000 loading cycles at a pressure of 10-90% of the maximum service application pressure. In that way, it's possible to calculate degradation factors related to temperature, chemical resistance and cyclic service and finally, using an algorithm failure the long-term design envelope is determined. [8]

Another ageing method is the Arrhenius approach [1], which in physical chemistry originally related temperature and rates of concentration changes in chemically reactive liquid solutions. With materials, this approach has been found to apply to rates of property level changes, especially modulus for elastomers [9], which are also cross-linkable. Using elevated temperature as an accelerator, the material can absorb fluid that can affect the molecular chain in a reasonable test time. Measurements of changes in modulus from ageing can be plotted logarithmically against linear time at each temperature:

$$k = Ae^{-\left(\frac{E_a}{RT}\right)} \quad (1)$$

where rate k can be either the reciprocal of t - the time for a property level to reach a chosen percentage of its original value when aged at temperature T (degrees K) - or the gradient of the plot of property level versus time at T ; R is the gas constant; A is a constant, and E_a is the activation energy. A series of plots of property level versus reciprocal time is needed from separate tests at different temperatures T , each test yielding one point for the Arrhenius plot of k versus $1/T$ - which should be linear; if required, if the selected property level change equates to a defined failure criterion, extrapolation down to service temperature can then yield a lifetime prediction.

A semi-empirical approach to simulate ageing is to relate effects of ageing in GRPs to those of corrosion in metals, as the macro-level results are very similar. For example, a result of uniform corrosion is material loss for metals [1], and material loss can also affect GRPs. According to this approach, a relationship for uniform "corrosion" behaviour of GRPs in chlorine dioxide environments has been applied (Bergman 2004) [1]:

$$\varphi = Bt^\alpha cAe^{-\frac{E_a}{RT}} \quad (2)$$

where φ is the depth of "corrosion" (mm); B is a special factor for the case of protective deposits on

the surface (usually $B = 0$ or 1); t is the time in service (years); α is a factor that depends on the thickness and the degree of degradation of the surface layer (usually α is between 0.5 and 1); c is the concentration of chlorine dioxide (g/l); A is a material constant that depends on the type of resin, the degree of curing and the laminate structure; E_a is the activation energy of the rate-controlling step of the degradation process (J/mol); R is the general gas constant and T is the temperature (K).

To summarise, in the above mentioned methods, short term tests are used to account for such degradation and to give sufficient safety factors. There is apparently no method other than the Arrhenius approach for quantifying these effects for long term exposures and defining which effects are responsible for the degradation. The work described herein seeks to develop methodology to give data using relatively short term tests for accelerated exposure routines to predict long term performance. Comparisons of prediction and assessment of effects of ageing in industry is also scheduled.

Further to this, the ageing of GRPs and polymers is still commonly referred to in terms of 'corrosion technology' which is more akin to metals, often following oxidative attack. More appropriate terminology should be used (such as 'ageing', 'chemical resistance' and 'degradation') for referring to non-metals.

Ageing in Industry

Ageing is related to in industry as the reduction in performance of a component as a function of the applied conditions. [1] However, it is important to define the mechanisms by which the material is ageing, and the stages through which the material property levels degrade.

Referring to Fig. 2, fluid absorption commences immediately at the inner surface of the pipe (Stage 1) and physical changes occur. At Stage 2, there is further diffusion through the thickness and the inner surface may begin to age chemically (as this surface is in constant contact with the fluid). Further fluid diffusion and chemical ageing continue in Stage 3, but the forming of cracks on the inner surface results in quicker fluid diffusion to the inner plies of the material. In Stage 4, diffusion, chemical ageing and mechanical damage has continued, but now the mechanical damage on the inner surface is sufficient to cause material to be removed.

Finally, in Stage 5, there is complete damage and subsequent leaking. In the oil and gas industry, definition of failure criteria depends on the type of equipment and the consequences of failure, but equipment should be designed to work until Stage 3.

However, failure somewhere between Stages 2 and 3 is the ideal target for designers, in order to minimize the risk of sudden catastrophic failure.

Fig. 2 Several stages for ageing of a GRP pipe

Much work has been done to establish failure modes in service and as a result three common types of failure for composite pipes are presented: (i) Weeping, implying passage of liquid through cracks, (ii) Burst, which means failure of the fibres, and (iii) Strain Corrosion, which is a combination of resin cracks and fibre rupture, and of bending strains in corrosive media. Other less common failure modes focus on leakages in pipe connections or due to impact damage. [10]

(i) Weeping failure is controlled only by the resin and occurs in pipes under high strains. The creation and growth of cracks allow passage of liquid. [10, 11]

(ii) Burst failure is controlled only by the fibres and measures the ability of the glass fibres to resist the chemical attack by liquid. [12]

(iii) Strain Corrosion failure is controlled both by resin and the fibres. It is designed as a combination of bending loads whilst in contact with an aggressive chemical. [13]

Experimental Approach

A test programme was defined to look into the changes in material property magnitudes, resulting through exposure to various environments with

temperature and time. The main object of this work is to understand how the ageing factors affect the material and try to develop a methodology to predict the service life of a pipe. The procedure not only enables saturation of the material and hence a life prediction study to be conducted, but also enables progression of ageing to be monitored through the thickness of the wall, through single side exposure of pipe wall sections.

Materials used for this approach were common GRP pipes, with vinyl-ester resin and glass fibres. Also, there were two protective layers, one on each of the outside and inside surfaces. The outer surface was covered with a vinyl-ester resin layer (the veil) and the inner surface was also covered with a vinyl-ester resin layer (the liner). The reason for these is to work as diffusion barriers and protect the structural part of the pipe from ageing mechanisms.

First of all, for both physical and chemical ageing, the value of the diffusion coefficient, D , needed to be measured. Specimens of GRP pipes were cut at appropriate dimensions following the ASTM D5229 [14] and immersed, i.e. all surfaces were exposed in standard laboratory seawater according to ASTM D1141 [15]. In ideal Fickian behaviour, water absorption increases linearly with the square root of time for values, according to the standard, of $M_t/M_\infty \leq 0.5$ (where M_t is the total amount of moisture absorbed at time t and M_∞ is the total amount absorbed at equilibrium). Diffusion can also be calculated according to ASTM D5229:

$$D = \pi \left(\frac{h}{4M_m} \right)^2 \left(\frac{M_2 - M_1}{\sqrt{t_2} - \sqrt{t_1}} \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

where h is the average specimen thickness; M_m is the effective water equilibrium content, %, and $\frac{M_2 - M_1}{\sqrt{t_2} - \sqrt{t_1}}$ is the slope of water absorption plot for the initial linear part of the curve.

In that way the diffusion coefficient was calculated. Then, having the diffusion rate, the average diffusion distance into the material can be determined by

$$\bar{x} = \sqrt{2Dt} \quad (4)$$

where D is the diffusion coefficient of the materials and t is the time of the exposure.

In order to monitor mechanical property levels following more representative service conditions (i.e. exposing the inside of the pipe only), a method for conducting single sided exposures has been

developed, based on an aluminium plate which is in bonded with an adhesive to one surface of the sample, therefore isolating one side of the material from the environment (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 Single side exposure specimens using aluminium plate to cover the surface

The progress of ageing was monitored by means of mechanical testing. For this, flexural (ASTM D790) [16], tensile (ASTM D638) [17] and short beam strength (ASTM D2344) [18] specimens were used. In addition to testing specimens, testing of pipe sections also took place, with rings cut from the pipes, to allow measurement of the apparent hoop compression strength (ASTM D2412) [19].

Ageing exposures were performed on the pipe before specimens were cut out. To do this, the pipe was filled with the test seawater, and metal end caps attached to seal the open ends of the pipe. The assembly (Fig. 4) was seated on a heater plate and this, together with an internal cartridge heater, was used to increase the temperature of the seawater. In that way, service temperature and inside pressure were simulated. After the exposure, test specimens were machined out for mechanical tests.

Fig. 4 Pipe section tests setup

An additional approach for characterizing changes due to chemical ageing has been to measure dynamic T_g with established DMA tests.

Results, Extra Test Development and Discussion

Material 1

Specimens from material 1, a vinyl-ester resin with glass fibre reinforcement, were immersed into seawater for more than two months to lead to calculation of the diffusion coefficient. In order to accelerate the process, three temperatures were chosen to be higher than the service temperature, but at least 20°C lower than the glass transition temperature of the material. After the exposure, there were obvious marks of damage (Fig. 5), such as discoloration and cracks both in the inner surface of the specimen (liner) and the outer surface (veil). Regarding the seawater mass uptake absorption plot (Fig 6), there was an increase in the mass of less than 2% at 60°C; however, at 80°C there was an increase in water absorption until 2% at almost 40 days of exposure, after which the mass started decreasing significantly). The same profile is seen for 100°C, but, faster (in 14 days). It is possible that a similar observation will eventually occur at 60°C - this test is still underway.

Fig. 5 Material 1 specimen for liquid uptake tests (unaged – left and after exposure at 100°C – right)

The sharp decrease was possibly caused by the cracks that appeared in the liner and in the veil. Possibly, the water absorption of the sample affected the stiffness of the liner and the veil. As a result, thermal stresses developed and made their appearance. In addition, from the profiles of these plots, leaching of soluble species from specimens

was apparently happening, perhaps from as early as 1 day's ageing, to exacerbate the development of thermal stresses. It is possible that the leaching, having accelerated the onset of cracking in this way, is then itself increased dramatically by the appearance of the cracks, with increased surface area and shorter distances to be diffused by the leaching species.

Fig. 6 Moisture absorption plot for material 1

The diffusion coefficient was calculated for unprotected specimens for the period before any cracks were observed. An average diffusion coefficient for the three different temperatures and the expected diffusion depth were calculated using equation 3 and 4 and are presented in Table 1. It should be mentioned that D_{av} was calculated for different times for each temperature, before cracks were observed.

Temperature (°C)	D_{av} (mm ² /s)	\bar{x} (mm)
60°C	$1.58e^{-7}$	3.1
80°C	$2.81e^{-7}$	3.1
100°C	$6.31e^{-7}$	3.1

Table 1 Average values for Diffusion coefficient and depth

It is clear that there is a relationship between temperature and diffusion coefficient, and whilst the temperature is increasing, the GRP absorbs water faster and reaches the equilibrium quicker.

Concerning the uni-directional diffusion through the wall thickness from single sided exposures, some contradictory results were obtained with the first attempts. Due to different thermal coefficients of GRP specimens and aluminium, the thermal stresses were higher than the maximum strength of the adhesive used, and as a result cracks occurred on

that surface, creating a path for extra water ingress in that region, which is clearly indicated in Fig. 4 seen as salt residues on the protected surface. Moreover, in Fig. 8, the plot of the single side exposure specimens is shown above that for the unprotected samples; this unexpectedly means more absorption from the so-called protected specimens, showing that the protection had failed as outlined above.

Figure 7 Single side exposure specimen after 19 days at 80°C in sea water

Figure 8 Single side mass uptake graphs after 19 days at 80°C in simulated sea water

As a result, a new technique has now been developed whereby a section of pipe is sealed over a small aluminium alloy 'bath' (Fig. 9), the top of which is machined to match the inner radius of the pipe section to ensure there is no leakage. This ensures that, with the specimen tightly clamped in place, diffusion only occurs through the thickness of

the material, from a single side. Moreover, with a valve it is possible to monitor and control the internal pressure. The procedure is still being developed and results cannot yet be published.

Figure 9 Single side exposure prototype

Concerning mechanical tests, firstly, flexural tests were conducted to try to investigate any change in the behaviour of the material. A drop in the maximum strength (Fig. 10) with a different failure mode for the unaged and aged specimens was observed, the latter being more rapid; the unaged material showed distortion in the structural pipe material concentrated around the crack tip, whereas the aged specimens showed no visible damage (or discoloration) beyond the liner (Fig. 11).

Figure 10 Comparison between ageing regimes – Flexural Tests

Upon reaching the interface, the crack then appeared to run along the interface between the liner and the structural pipe material, with some cracks extending through the plies into the structural material before running between plies. Previous research has indicated hydrolysis of ether bonds [20], which

means that the resin deteriorates with increasing exposure to immersion environments. So it can be assumed that ageing has affected only the liner and the interface between the liner and the structural part of the pipe.

Figure 11 Detailed view of crack for unaged and aged specimens after flexural tests

Tensile tests were then conducted and showed a reduction in the maximum load (Fig. 12), but the modulus was unaffected.

Figure 12 Comparison between ageing regimes – Tensile Tests

Figure 13 Detailed view of crack for unaged and aged specimens after tensile tests

From these plots, it has been assumed that the failure of the specimens occurred at the first load decrease, which happened when the liner cracked. The crack was observed at 90° to the load path (Fig. 13). After the crack point, it was also observed that the local strains were very similar both for unaged and aged specimens, again indicating that perhaps only the liner was affected by the ageing mechanisms, and not the structural part of the pipe.

In hoop compression tests, failure occurred where the load applied resulted in liner cracking (Fig. 14). A radial crack then propagated through the thickness until it reached the structural pipe material; it then propagated circumferentially away from the radial crack along the interface between the structural pipe and the liner. A decrease in the load for the aged specimens was recorded (Fig. 15). Combining these factors again indicates that the liner has been affected by ageing mechanisms.

Figure 14 Detailed view of failure for unaged and aged specimens after hoop compression tests

Figure 15 Comparison between ageing regimes – Hoop Compression Tests

Moreover, it should be mentioned that the drop in the load was similar to flexural tests. This would be expected as both tests put the inner surface of the pipe (liner) under tension.

Material 2

Specimens of Material 2, also vinyl-ester resin with glass fibre reinforcement, were exposed to UV radiation in order to simulate situations when pipes are on the ground with the outer surface exposed to sunlight. Discoloration is the first thing that was observed after the end of the exposure (Fig. 16).

Figure 16 Comparison between before and after UV exposure

Flexural, Short beam strength and DMA tests have been carried out to investigate any changes due to ageing. Flexural tests have shown an increase both in flexural modulus and maximum strength (Fig. 17), although failure modes were the same, with the veil cracking first (Fig. 18). UV radiation showed no degradation in flexural properties, which is in agreement with previous work which reported that UV only affects only the outer micrometres of the resin matrix [20]. The higher break load probably arose from further curing, giving more cross-links and eliminating any possible moisture.

Figure 17 Comparison between ageing regimes – Flexural Tests

Figure 18 Detailed view of failure for unaged and aged specimens after flexural tests

Short beam strength tests also showed an increase in strength after UV exposure (Fig. 19). For both occasions failure modes were the same and all specimens failed with the liner in tension directly beneath the loading roller (Fig. 20), which is acceptable under the ASTM D2344 standard.

Figure 19 Comparison between ageing regimes – Short Beam Shear Tests

Figure 20 Detailed view of failure for un-aged and aged specimens after short beam strength tests

DMA tests indicated a 2-3°C increase in T_g for the specimen aged by UV, presumably again due to further curing (Fig. 21 and 22).

Figure 21 DMA results for unaged specimen

Figure 22 DMA results after UV radiation

Conclusion

Nowadays, GRP pipes are installed for hundreds of kilometers over hostile terrains because of their improved performance over steel in corrosive

environments. However, failure can still occur eventually, and may cause several problems both in the industry and the environment without adequate prior predictions arising from appropriate laboratory work.

The research reported herein marks initial development of a test methodology for understanding appropriate ageing mechanisms and how they affect the material through the thickness. It focuses on seawater exposures. It is shown that, if protective thermoplastic liners eventually succumb, subsequent ageing of the GRP mainly involves the GRP matrix, which protects the glass reinforcement.

Results included observation of leaching effects and cracks; they have significant effect on mass uptake tests. Rationale has been proposed for exposing material from a single side only.

The liner acts as a diffusion barrier, protecting the structural layers of the pipe, so for further research, it can be assumed that when it is affected by ageing mechanisms, the pipe should be repaired or replaced. Concerning UV exposure, it only affects the surface, without degrading further layers of the material. The findings obtained could be explained; more research is needed to fully understand all the ageing mechanisms and how they applied through the wall thickness of the pipe.

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